

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.5382 Max: 62.6243	1394 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1790 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: Ashlar Blocks BELOW 1384/1388
 Covered by: SU: 1388 Fills: SU: Filled by: SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX	
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash		
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones		
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt	<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth	Compaction	
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand	<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt	<input type="checkbox"/> Shells	<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass			<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	
			Color	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)
 Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original
 Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1400 (VIA CLAUDIA); WALL 1058; ON EAST; LOWER TUFO FLOOR
Is covered by: 1384/1388	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
 ONE CONTINUOUS PIECE THAT HAS BEEN CUT TO FORM A STEP, RELATION W/ BLOCK BN WEST (THAT GOES INTO WALL 1058) REQUIRES FURTHER EXCAVATION

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: SOUTH-WESTERN EDGE
 Shape: 2 rectangular steps made from a monolithic block

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify):

□ = ashlar blocks

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: East-West (so entrance could have been from South → North)

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Solid block

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Expertly cut stone, one solid block cut into 2 "steps". Top step is 190x32cm with an 8cm drop to second/lower step which is 243x24cm. The lower step continues 23cm on the west past the top step and 30cm on the east.

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

ONE SOLID ASHLAR CUT INTO 2 "STEPS" (GOING DOWN TOWARD NORTH) OF THRESHOLD LEADING FROM VIA CLAUDIA SU1400 INTO COURTYARD SITUATED W/ WALL 1058 ALONG WESTERN SIDE. SU1394 ASHLAR BLOCK APPEARS TO BE ASSOCIATED WITH A LOWER TUFO FLOOR PHASE (SU# TBA) BELOW TUFO FLOOR 1173 (AS SEEN ON SOUTHWESTERN EDGE OF 1173.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	<u>SIL</u>	on	<u>19/7/2011</u>
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